

FULL FIELD MAPPING OF FOAM DEFORMATION PATTERN AT MICROSCALES

F.P. Chiang
Stony Brook University
Department of Mechanical Engineering
Stony Brook, NY 11794-2300
Fu-pen.chiang@stonybrook.edu

SUMMARY

The multi-scale digital speckle photography technique is described in detail. Applications of this technique to foam composites at micro scales are presented showing unusual deformation patterns under various loading conditions.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Sandwich panels with foam core have gained substantial importance in marine applications for over 60 years to lighten, stiffen, and strengthen the boat structures [1]. The decreased weight helps to increase top speed and acceleration, increase cargo capacity, and reduce operating and maintenance cost. The increased stiffness and strength allow builders to use less skin material resulting in even lower weight structure. The sandwich structure consisting of a foam core and two skins has many advantages including better thermal insulation, better impact/damage resistance, longer fatigue life, and sound attenuation. Foam core materials have been studied by many investigators [2-8]. In most cases, the foam cores were treated as homogeneous and isotropic materials. This assumption does not have a physical base in that core materials are in general not homogeneous nor isotropic in the macro-domain as well as the micro-domain. Experimental testings are mostly done with macro-specimen and by analyzing global responses.

In this paper we present some results of mapping a foam core's deformation at micro length scales. We show that many conventional concepts of the deformation and failure modes are not applicable at these scales.

Essential to all these studies is a unique experimental mechanics technique called digital speckle photography. In the following this special technique will be presented first before the studies of foam composites are presented.

2. THE DIGITAL SPECKLE PHOTOGRAPHY TECHNIQUE

Using a random pattern for quantitative displacement/strain measurement is a major milestone in the history of experimental stress/strain analysis. Heretofore,

measurement of deformation is done by using a regular geometric pattern (grating, grid, optical markers, fringes, etc.) whose deviation from the norm is used as a gauge of deformation. The speckle methods [9-13], on the other hand, employ a random dot pattern (i.e., speckles) as a measuring gauge. Quantitative measurement is not done by direct comparison; rather it is obtained by maximizing the cross correlation between the random pattern before and after displacement/deformation. In the following we described a multi-scale digital speckle photography technique whereby the displacement sensitivity and spatial resolution can be varied by judiciously selecting the proper speckle size and recording magnification [9,13].

A random light intensity distribution of any sort can be considered as a speckle pattern, which may be naturally present or artificially created on the surface (or interior) of a specimen. The speckle pattern is digitally recorded sequentially before and after deformation and processed using a specially designed algorithm called Computer Aided Speckle Interferometry (CASI) [12]. The essence of CASI is described in the following. Two speckle patterns, one before and one after deformation, are first segmented into subimages of 32x32 pixels, for example, and the displacement of all points within a subimage is assumed to be constant.

Fig. 1 Schematic of CASI for calculating displacement vectors.

The corresponding subimages of the two recordings are “compared” via a two-step FFT (fast Fourier transform) process to find the displacement vector. Figure 1 is the schematic of the CASI process. In Figure 1, $h_1(x,y)$ is the complex amplitudes of the light disturbance of a generic speckle subimages before deformation and $h_2(x,y)$ is nothing but the original speckle pattern with displacement components added, i.e.,

$$h_2(x, y) = h_1[x - u(x, y), y - v(x, y)]$$

where u and v are the displacement components along the x and y directions, respectively, of the subimage “point”. First a FFT is applied to both h_1 and h_2 . Then, a numerical “interference” between the two speckle patterns is performed on the spectral domain as follows,

$$F(\omega_x, \omega_y) = \frac{H_1(\omega_x, \omega_y)H_2^*(\omega_x, \omega_y)}{\sqrt{|H_1(\omega_x, \omega_y)H_2(\omega_x, \omega_y)|}}$$

$$= \sqrt{|H_1(\omega_x, \omega_y)H_2(\omega_x, \omega_y)|} \exp\{j[\phi_1(\omega_x, \omega_y) - \phi_2(\omega_x, \omega_y)]\}$$

where $\phi_1(\omega_x, \omega_y)$ and $\phi_2(\omega_x, \omega_y)$ are the phases of $H_1(\omega_x, \omega_y)$ and $H_2(\omega_x, \omega_y)$, respectively, and * denotes complex conjugate. Finally, a halo function is obtained by a second FFT, i.e.,

$$G(\xi, \eta) = \mathfrak{F}\{F(\omega_x, \omega_y)\} = \overline{G}(\xi - u, \eta - v)$$

which is an expanded impulse function located at (u, v) of the ξ and η plane. Thus, by detecting the crest of this impulse function, the displacement vector represented by the cluster of speckles within the subimage is uniquely determined. Strains are then calculated using an appropriate strain-displacement relation. By recording the speckle image at incremental loads, strain of almost any finite magnitude can be obtained. At macro scales the texture of the foam cells themselves services as the speckle pattern. At microscales, SiC particles of micron size are spread onto the specimen surface to serve as speckle patterns. The speckle patterns at different stages of specimen deformation are recorded digitally via a CCD camera, an optical microscope, or a scanning electron microscope (SEM) [9,13]. Processing is performed using the CASI algorithm.

3. SIZE EFFECT ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF FOAM COMPOSITES

Fig. 2 Dimensions of the large and small polyurethane foam specimens.

Uniaxial tension specimens of the dog-bone type were machined from neat polyurethane foam panels. Figure 2 shows two types of specimens that were used in the experiments. The dimensions of the uniform section of the larger ones are 80mm×16mm×8mm whereas those of the smaller ones are 25mm×4.8mm×3.6mm. The larger specimens were tested using a tabletop InstronTM 1011 uniaxial testing machine, and the smaller ones were tested inside the vacuum chamber of a Hitachi S-2460N SEM at 30x, 100x and 300x magnifications, respectively. A thin coating of silicon carbide powder (with average powder size of about 20 μm for the larger specimens and 1 μm for the smaller specimens) was spread on the foam surface to serve as speckles. The specimen was loaded slowly under displacement control. After every incremental loading, the load was stopped and the speckle image was recorded after the force

reached steady state (the force drops slightly due to material's viscoelastic effect). The force was read from a load cell and strain was calculated using CASI.

contour interval is 18 μm

Fig. 3 Displacement fields of a macro specimen under uniaxial tension.

Figure 3 depicts a typical deformation pattern of a larger specimen as calculated by CASI. The lines represent displacement contours along x- (u field) and y-directions (v field), respectively. The contour interval is 18 μm . The distribution of the contours indicates that the deformation is fairly uniform, as one would expect from a uniaxially loaded tensile specimen. Thus at this scale, the material behaves as if it were rather homogeneous and isotropic.

At 30 \times (contour interval is 8 μm)

At 100 \times (contour interval is 1 μm)

At 300× (contour interval is 0.7 μm)

Fig. 4 Heterogeneous deformation as the observation length scales is reduced.

However, when the observation scale is reduced, interesting deformation patterns are observed. Figure 4 shows the deformation pattern of a small specimen tested inside the chamber of a scanning electron microscope. The contour intervals are 8 μm for 30x, 1 μm for 100x, and 0.7 μm for 300x images. The deformation pattern becomes progressively heterogeneous as the length scale is further reduced.

Figure 5 shows the stress strain relationships of all neat polyurethane foam specimens tested. The stress is the average stress obtained by dividing the load by the initial cross-sectional area of the specimen and the strain is the average value of strains in all subimages. As can be seen from the figure the material is highly non-linear and the stress-strain curve is size dependent. And for a given size the result also depends on the dimension of the area from which the strain is measured. The general trend is that larger specimens show a higher stiffness. This may be attributed to the fact that the material is a porous one consisting of interconnected foam cells. When the specimen is large enough the mutual constraints of the cells give rise to the stiffness of the foam. When the specimen size is reduced, the ratio of cell size to the specimen cross-section is increased. As a result, the material effectively becomes more “porous”, hence the reduced stiffness.

Fig. 5 Stress-strain curves of various specimens.

4. CRACK TIP DEFORMATION IN FOAM AT DIFFERENT LENGTH SCALES

Knowing the crack tip deformation field is of course essential to understanding the crack growth behavior and the resulting fracture of a material. Foam is neither homogeneous nor isotropic at a length scale of the order of its unit cell. Unlike common structural materials such as aluminum or steel in which the size of a crystal is many orders of magnitude smaller than the macro length scale used in the structural, the cell size in a foam is only about two to three orders of magnitude smaller than the macro length used in a sandwich structural construct. Thus, it is important that its behavior at different length scales be examined before a realistic predictive model can be constructed. In the following we examine the crack tip deformation of a beam made of PVC foam under a three-point bending load. Fig. 6 depicts some of the results. On the left is a pair of micrographs showing the region in which we performed the CASI analysis. The upper picture, taken at 50x magnification shows the tip of a crack created by a sharp razor blade cut which is visible near the bottom of the picture. The region just above the crack tip, marked by a black rectangle is further enlarged to 100x. CASI was used to map the region's deformation pattern and the results are shown in the two

sets of u - and v - field displacement contours depicted. The displacement sensitivity of the contours are $2\ \mu\text{m}$ and $1\ \mu\text{m}$, respectively, for the 50x and 100x pictures. At the 50x magnification, the crack tip deformation patterns show only a small resemblance to that of the classical deformation pattern at the crack tip. At 100x magnification, the formation pattern bears no similarity to that of the classical pattern at all. Thus, if one is to construct a realistic analytical or numerical model to predict the deformation of a foam beam or plate under load, these types of deformation must be taken into consideration.

Fig. 6 Crack tip deformation field of a nano-phased PVC foam specimen with an edge crack under 3-point bending.

Crack propagation in a foam material is also quite different from that of a traditional engineering material. Fig. 7 depicts the characteristics of crack propagation in foam at a micro-scale. The specimen is a coupon with a single edge crack under tension. When the load is increased, voids spontaneously appear in front of the crack. Further loading results in blunting of the original crack as well as the enlargement of the void. Eventually, the main crack and the void are linked together resulting in failure of the specimen. The last picture in the figure depicts the deformation of a step loading after the void has been generated. The displacement vector field demonstrates an interesting deformation pattern: all the vectors are pointing towards the crack tip region.

Fig. 7 Crack propagation characteristics in a foam at a micro scale.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

We have introduced a multi-scale digital speckle technique for mapping deformation fields of foam at different length scales. At micro-scales, the deformation field is rather complicated and cannot be predicted by the existing theoretical models.

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References

1. Vinson JR, Rajapakse YDS, Carlsson L (Eds.) (2003) Proc. of 6th Int Conf Sandw Struct, Ft. Lauderdale, FL
2. Prasad S, Carlsson L (1994) Debonding and crack kinking in foam core sandwich beams – I. analysis of fracture specimens. Eng Fract Mech 47(6):813-824
3. Prasad S, Carlsson L (1994) Debonding and crack kinking in foam core sandwich beams – II. experimental investigation. Eng Fract Mech 47(6):825-841
4. Gibson LJ, Ashby MF, Schajer GS, Robertsson CI (1982) The mechanics of two-dimensional cellular materials. Proc R Soc London A382:25-42

5. Gibson LJ, Ashby MF (1982) The mechanics of three-dimensional cellular materials. *Proc R Soc London A*382:43-59
6. Zenkert D, Bäcklund J (1989) PVC sandwich core materials: Mode I fracture toughness. *Compos Sci Technol* 34:225-242
7. Zenkert D (1989) PVC sandwich core materials: fracture behaviour under mode II and mixed mode conditions. *Mater. Sci. Eng. A*108:233-240
8. Hallström S, Grenestedt JL (1997) Mixed mode fracture of cracks and wedge shaped notches in expanded PVC foam. *Int J of Fract* 88(4):343-358
9. Chiang FP (2003) Evolution of white light speckle method and its application to micro/nanotechnology and heart mechanics. *Opt Eng* 42(5):1288-1292
10. Chiang FP (1978) A family of 2D and 3D experimental stress analysis techniques using laser speckles. *Solid Mech Archives* 3(1):1-32
11. Chen DJ, Chiang FP (1993) Computer aided speckle interferometry using spectral amplitude fringes. *Appl Opt* 3(2):225-236
12. Chen DJ, Chiang FP, Tan YS, Don HS (1993) Digital speckle-displacement measurement using a complex spectrum method. *Appl Opt* 32(11):1839-1849
13. Chiang FP, Wang Q, Lehman F (1997) New developments in full field strain measurements using speckles. In: Lucas GF, Stubbs DA, (ed) *Nontraditional methods of sensing stress, strain and damage in materials and structures*. ASTM STP 1318:156-169
14. Lakes RS (1987) Foam structures with a negative Poisson's ratio. *Sci* 235:1038-1040